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Impact of digital literacy on the adoption of precision agriculture and its effect on the sustainability of rice cultivation in Lambayeque

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The transition to more sustainable and climate-resilient agriculture is an urgent challenge in agricultural regions of developing countries such as Lambayeque (Peru), especially in rice cultivation. In this context, digital literacy is emerging as a key enabler for accessing climate data, adopting precision agriculture technologies, and implementing sustainable agricultural practices. However, there are gaps linked to sociodemographic variables such as age, which can moderate these technology adoption processes. The objective of this study was to analyze the patterns of association between digital literacy, access to finance, risk perception, and the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices, and to examine whether age moderates the association between digital literacy and access to climate data. To this end, a quantitative, non-experimental approach was applied, using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The sample consisted of 101 rice farmers in the Lambayeque region, who were given a validated questionnaire that included five theoretical constructs measured using Likert scales. The results of the structural model confirmed that digital literacy has a positive and significant association with access to climate data ($\beta = 0.461$, $p < 0.001$) and with the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices ($\beta = 0.259$, $p = 0.015$). A positive association was identified between access to finance and risk perception ($\beta = 0.411$, $p < 0.001$). Age was negatively associated with digital literacy ($\beta = -0.196$; $p = 0.027$); however, the formal moderation test (DL \times Age) was not significant ($\beta = -0.054$, $p = 0.421$), so there is no evidence that age moderates the association between digital skills and access to climate information. These findings support the design of differentiated interventions that incorporate intergenerational digital training, inclusive financing policies, and hybrid technology transfer strategies tailored to access gaps. Taken together, the evidence is consistent with the idea that reducing the digital divide can strengthen agricultural sustainability and climate resilience in rural contexts in Latin America.

KEYWORDS

climate change, digital literacy, PLS-SEM, precision agriculture, sustainability, technology adoption

1 Introduction

The transformation of agricultural systems toward sustainable, efficient, and climate-resilient models is an urgent challenge for the rural economies of developing countries (Finger et al., 2019). This challenge is especially critical in the Lambayeque region (Peru), where agriculture, and rice cultivation in particular, faces increasing pressures from climate variability, water resource depletion, and market fluctuations (Rahim et al., 2022). In this context, many producers continue to operate using traditional practices that limit their ability to respond to climate risks and reduce their competitiveness in increasingly technified agricultural environments (Bucci et al., 2020). Low digital literacy and limited adoption of precision agriculture technologies perpetuate productivity and sustainability gaps, restricting the innovation and adaptation potential of local farmers (Lu et al., 2024; Mu et al., 2024).

Over the past 5 years, research in precision agriculture has experienced remarkable growth, with approaches that integrate emerging technologies, big data analysis, and rural digitization processes aimed at improving agricultural sustainability and productivity (Finger et al., 2019; Rahim et al., 2022). One of the most consistent areas of focus is the development of systems that combine multispectral sensors, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and predictive models to optimize agricultural practices (Bucci et al., 2020; Sangaiah et al., 2024).

Finger et al. (2019) highlight that precision agriculture lies at the intersection between production efficiency and environmental impact mitigation, establishing itself as a very important tool in sustainable intensification strategies. Along the same lines, Bucci et al. (2020) show that the perception of economic benefits is a key determinant for its sustained adoption. In addition, Sangaiah et al. (2024) proposed UAV T-YOLO-Rice, a deep learning-based system for high-precision rice panicle detection, demonstrating the potential of these technologies to improve real-time monitoring and data collection. For their part, Rahim et al. (2022) analyzed the economic impact of precision agriculture applied to rice cultivation, highlighting tangible benefits in terms of profitability, sustainability, and rational use of inputs, aspects of particular interest in producing regions such as Lambayeque.

In the field of digitization, the importance of digital skills as an enabling factor for technology adoption has been highlighted. Lu et al. (2024) demonstrated that digital literacy has a significant impact on agricultural productivity and the willingness to incorporate smart technologies. Complementarily, Mu et al. (2024) showed that the influence of social networks and the demonstration effect among farmers promote collective adoption processes, highlighting the role of community and cognitive factors in the incorporation of innovations.

Although the studies reviewed document important advances in the adoption of precision technologies and digital literacy (Lu et al., 2024), there remains a gap in the understanding of the structural interactions between these factors and variables such as risk perception and access to finance (Bucci et al., 2020). This gap is especially noticeable in rural contexts in Latin America, where sociocultural and economic dynamics condition technological adoption in different ways (Rahim et al., 2022). This research

seeks to provide empirical evidence that contributes to filling this gap through an integrative approach based on structural equation modeling.

This study is justified by the need to generate empirical evidence that allows us to understand how digital literacy, risk perception, and access to strategic resources, such as financing and climate data, interact in the adoption of precision agriculture practices and sustainability. The Lambayeque region is an ideal setting for this analysis, given its agricultural importance and the structural challenges faced by its producers. Understanding these links will not only contribute to scientific knowledge but also provide valuable input for the design of public policies and interventions that promote more digitally informed, resilient, and environmentally responsible agriculture. The application of the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach will allow us to identify causal paths and mediating relationships that have not yet been sufficiently explored in the literature. The objective of this study is to analyze the structural relationships between digital literacy, risk perception, access to financing, and the adoption of precision agriculture technologies and sustainable practices, using PLS-SEM. The research focuses on rice producers in the Lambayeque region, with the aim of providing contextualized evidence to facilitate the formulation of strategies for strengthening digital capabilities, reducing perceived barriers, and promoting technological innovation in rural environments.

2 Theoretical framework

Within this theoretical framework, Figure 1 shows the conceptual model proposed in this research, describing the structural relationships between the variables evaluated using PLS-SEM. It suggests that digital literacy (DL) is significantly associated with access to climate data (ACD) and the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP). Age showed no evidence of moderating the DL → ACD relationship. Instead, it was negatively associated with digital literacy (DL) and, through this channel, indirectly linked to lower access to climate data (ACD). The model allows us to explore how digital skills, access to strategic resources, and sociodemographic characteristics are associated with agricultural sustainability in rural contexts.

2.1 Digital literacy in the context of agriculture

Digital literacy refers to the skills needed to use digital technologies in agronomic decision-making, accessing relevant data, and implementing sustainable practices (Balyan et al., 2024; Carolan, 2017). In rural areas, these skills enable farmers to operate tools such as mobile applications, remote sensors, and geographic information systems, which are essential for addressing the challenges of climate change and improving production efficiency (Chunfang et al., 2024; Finger et al., 2019).

Thus, in the agricultural context, digital literacy is conceived as a set of skills that enable farmers to interact effectively with digital technologies applied to production. This definition includes key

operational components: mastery of devices and applications, such as mobile phones, remote sensors, and geographic information systems (GIS), used to monitor crops and plan agronomic decisions; data interpretation, which involves the ability to read and apply agroclimatic information in real time; and digital security and privacy, understood as basic knowledge about personal data protection and the responsible use of digital platforms in rural environments. These elements allow the construct to be defined more precisely and reflect its relevance in the transition to more informed, efficient, and sustainable agriculture.

Recent studies show that farmers with higher digital literacy are more likely to adopt sustainable technologies and have a lower perception of risk when it comes to innovation (Kitole et al., 2024; Mu et al., 2024; Rajak et al., 2023). Furthermore, these skills contribute to improved crop planning, rational use of inputs, and ecological resilience (Lu et al., 2024; SaberiKamarposhti et al., 2024).

2.2 Relationship between digital literacy (DL) and access to climate data (ACD): recent evidence

Digital literacy significantly improves farmers' ability to access and interpret climate information, facilitating the adoption of sustainable practices (Lu et al., 2024). The use of digital platforms also promotes collective learning and the exchange of experiences, strengthening confidence in the use of technologies (Mu et al., 2024).

From a systemic perspective, digital literacy acts as a cross-cutting enabler that allows farmers to interact effectively with the contemporary technological and agricultural knowledge environment. By improving their digital skills, producers can access relevant and timely information on sustainable practices, interpret climate and soil data, and use emerging technologies

that promote more efficient and environmentally responsible production. This capacity also increases confidence and willingness to adopt innovations by reducing the perception of uncertainty and facilitating a positive assessment of their medium- and long-term benefits.

The integration of monitoring systems, mobile applications, and agronomic management tools allows for the optimization of natural resource use (Bucci et al., 2020; Finger et al., 2019). Based on these arguments and evidence, it is proposed that greater digital literacy not only reduces technological barriers but also contributes directly to increasing producers' access to climate data. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1: Digital literacy (DL) shows a positive and significant association with access to climate data (ACD).

2.3 Impact of digital literacy (DL) on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP)

Digital literacy represents a comprehensive set of skills that enable farmers to interact effectively with emerging technologies and access key information to optimize their production decisions. In the context of contemporary agriculture, this skill has become a decisive factor in the transition to more sustainable practices, as it facilitates the search, understanding, and application of knowledge about management techniques that reduce environmental impact and improve resource use efficiency. Lu et al. (2024) highlight that farmers with higher levels of digital literacy show a greater capacity to adopt smart technologies that optimize water and fertilizer consumption, contributing to more responsible production.

This research clearly distinguishes between two concepts that, although related, respond to different approaches within agricultural transformation: the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAPs) and precision agriculture. Sustainable practices refer to actions aimed at conserving natural resources and reducing environmental impact, such as crop rotation, the use of organic fertilizers, integrated pest management, and efforts to maintain ecological balance. These practices can be implemented with or without the use of digital technologies and respond to a logic of sustainability based on traditional agronomic knowledge and ecological principles. On the other hand, precision agriculture involves the use of advanced technologies, such as multispectral sensors, geographic information systems (GIS), drones, and mobile applications, to optimize agronomic decision-making in real time. Although both strategies may converge in the pursuit of more efficient and responsible production, it is important to differentiate them conceptually in order to clearly delimit the constructs evaluated in the structural model.

The Sustainable Agricultural Practices Adoption (SAP) construct has been designed to comprehensively reflect the fundamental dimensions of sustainability in the agricultural context. The items that comprise it are not limited to the use of technologies, but also incorporate practices aimed at resource efficiency, such as rational fertilizer management, measured use of organic fertilizers, and irrigation planning, as well as actions that

promote a positive impact on the ecosystem, such as crop rotation, integrated pest management, and efforts to maintain ecological balance. These practices contribute directly to soil conservation, biodiversity, and resilience to climate change. In this way, the SAP construct allows for the evaluation of sustainable behaviors that integrate both traditional agronomic knowledge and the strategic use of technologies, without the latter being the only indicator of sustainability.

For their part, [Mu et al. \(2024\)](#) show that the use of digital platforms and mobile climate monitoring applications promotes collective learning and the creation of networks for sharing experiences, factors that reinforce confidence in the adoption of sustainable practices. These digital networks allow producers to share information on innovations, assess risks, and generate collaborative strategies aimed at productive and environmental sustainability.

Taken together, this evidence shows that digital literacy not only removes technological barriers but also creates an environment conducive to sustainable agricultural innovation by strengthening farmers' ability to appreciate the positive economic and environmental impact of sustainable practices. Therefore, it is proposed that a higher level of digital literacy has a positive impact on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices by facilitating their understanding, appreciation, and effective application.

Hypothesis 2: Higher levels of digital literacy (DL) are associated with greater adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP).

2.4 Digital literacy (DL) and its impact on risk perception (RP)

Digital literacy can improve farmers' ability to anticipate and manage climatic, economic, and regulatory risks ([Balyan et al., 2024](#); [Kitole et al., 2024](#)). However, this effect may depend on factors such as prior experience, trust in technology, and the local context ([Chowdhury et al., 2025](#)).

Furthermore, [Gumbi et al. \(2023\)](#) highlight that access to digital platforms expands farmers' ability to analyze climate information, market prices, and sustainable farming practices, which directly impacts their perception of production and economic risks. For their part, [Balyan et al. \(2024\)](#) emphasize that levels of digital literacy correlate positively with confidence in the use of technologies to mitigate risks. Evidence found by [Köhler et al. \(2024\)](#) also suggests that the development of digital skills reduces uncertainty and encourages the adoption of preventive measures in the face of emerging threats. Finally, [Rajak et al. \(2023\)](#) highlight that the ability to access and understand data significantly influences how farmers perceive market volatility and extreme weather events.

[Fonseka et al. \(2024\)](#) show that farmers with advanced digital skills are better able to use multispectral imaging technologies and other digital tools to monitor crops and anticipate problems, which impacts their perception of risk. Similarly, [Rajalakshmi et al. \(2024\)](#) highlight that the development of artificial intelligence-based models for crop prediction and classification is directly related to farmers' ability to understand and manage risks, which

in turn depends on their level of digital literacy. [Zhou et al. \(2024\)](#) point out that access to hyperspectral data and digital monitoring systems allows farmers to adjust decisions in real time, improving their perception and response to climate and production risks. [Wang et al. \(2024\)](#) add that the use of combined spectral and digital image data increases decision-making accuracy, reinforcing the perception of control and reducing uncertainty in the face of risk factors. Finally, [Chen et al. \(2024\)](#) conclude that the design of digital systems for targeted application of inputs helps reduce the perception of risk in the face of economic and environmental impacts, reinforcing the importance of digital literacy as a means of understanding and taking advantage of these technological tools.

Therefore, in the agricultural sector, risk perception refers to the producer's subjective judgment of the probability and consequences of adverse events that may affect their activity. This construct includes operational dimensions such as the probability of danger, understood as the expected frequency of extreme weather events, price fluctuations, or regulatory sanctions; and the expected consequence, which refers to the potential impact of such events on productivity, income, or the sustainability of the agricultural system. It also incorporates sensitivity to the environment, i.e., the farmer's level of awareness of emerging threats, and responsiveness, which reflects their perception of their ability to anticipate, mitigate, or adapt to risks through sustainable practices or the use of technologies. This definition allows us to analyze how farmers assess and cope with uncertainty in rural contexts that are vulnerable to climate change and digital transformation.

Digital literacy provides farmers with the skills they need to access timely information, understand complex data, and use technologies that enable them to efficiently manage the risks associated with agricultural activity. As farmers develop digital skills, they increase their ability to interpret and anticipate risks, which encourages more strategic and proactive decision-making. In this sense, it is logical to argue that greater digital literacy has a positive impact on risk perception by empowering farmers with cognitive and technical tools to deal with uncertainty, which allows us to propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3: Digital literacy (DL) is positively and significantly associated with risk perception (RP).

2.5 Access to climate data (ACD) and its relationship with the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAPs)

Several studies show that access to climate data has a positive influence on the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. For example, [Ashane and Senanayake \(2024\)](#) demonstrated that time series analysis using historical climate data allows farmers to adapt their cropping decisions to changing climate patterns, promoting sustainable strategies. [Zhou et al. \(2024\)](#) show that crop monitoring using sensors and hyperspectral imagery provides real-time information that facilitates sustainable adjustments in agricultural management. [Wang et al. \(2024\)](#) highlight that the integration of multispectral and climate data improves the accuracy of yield predictions, which strengthens sustainable decision-making.

SaberiKamarposhti et al. (2024) argue that AI-based agricultural technologies, powered by climate data, enable efficient, resilient practices with a smaller environmental footprint. Access to climate data provides an objective and predictive basis for farmers to reduce the uncertainty associated with climate change and adopt sustainable agricultural practices.

With accurate information on weather conditions, producers can make more informed decisions about the efficient use of inputs, prevent losses, and improve their practices to protect the environment. Therefore, it is proposed that the adoption of ACD has a positive and significant association with SAPs, as proposed in the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 4: Access to climate data (ACD) is positively associated with the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAPs).

2.6 Theoretical foundations of the link between access to climate data (ACD) and risk perception (RP)

Several studies have shown that the implementation of sustainable agricultural practices increases farmers' awareness of the risks associated with conventional agriculture. Aguilar-Luis et al. (2024) highlight that Peruvian farmers' exposure to sustainable techniques is associated with greater knowledge of the negative effects of agrochemicals on health and the environment. On the other hand, Nguyen et al. (2024) show that those producers who integrate sustainable practices into their activity are more sensitive to environmental risks, developing more responsible attitudes toward the effects of climate change. Thus, access to climate data not only represents a technical action, but also a transformation in the way farmers perceive the risk associated with the sustainability of their production systems (Aydogdu, 2020; Flores-Rojas et al., 2021).

From a socio-environmental perspective, it can be argued that access to climate data drives reflection and learning processes that strengthen risk perception among farmers. By incorporating technologies and methods that require greater technical knowledge and environmental awareness, agricultural producers develop a deeper understanding of the negative effects of traditional intensive practices. Consequently, ACD becomes a catalyst for cognitive change by promoting a more critical and preventive approach to agricultural, environmental, and economic risks.

Hypothesis 5: Access to climate data (ACD) has a positive and significant association with risk perception (RP).

2.7 Access to finance (AF) and its relationship with the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAPs)

The scientific literature supports the existence of a significant relationship between access to financing and the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices that are innovative for precision

agriculture. Financing allows for investment in technology and training, which facilitates the transition to more sustainable agriculture (Köhler et al., 2024; SaberiKamarposhti et al., 2024).

Similarly, Yang et al. (2024) point out that the digital economy and technology financing are important drivers for empowering farmers to adopt sustainable practices. Mark (2024) reinforces this view, highlighting that lack of financing is one of the main constraints to the implementation of precision agriculture technologies on small farms, while its availability promotes access to digital tools, improves yields, and encourages sustainable practices. For their part, Khaspuria et al. (2024) argue that access to specific lines of credit for precision technologies is a determining factor for the adoption of these practices in developing countries.

Access to financing acts as a relevant enabler for digital transformation in agriculture, reducing economic barriers and facilitating the adoption of precision technologies that improve the efficiency and sustainability of agricultural processes. In the absence of financing, farmers, especially small-scale farmers, face limitations in investing in technology, training, and sustainable practices, perpetuating cycles of low productivity and environmental degradation. Therefore, it is logical to assume that greater access to financial resources will enable farmers to implement innovative technological solutions, optimize the use of resources, and, consequently, strengthen sustainability in the agricultural sector, leading to the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 6: Access to finance (AF) has a positive and significant association with the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAPs).

2.8 Theoretical approach to the relationship between access to finance (AF) and risk perception (RP)

Access to finance is a crucial enabler of agricultural modernization, as it provides farmers with the resources necessary to invest in technology, training, and sustainable production practices (Khaspuria et al., 2024). This financial capacity not only facilitates the acquisition of inputs and equipment, but also promotes the adoption of monitoring and analysis tools that enable informed management of production and environmental risks.

Having financial resources improves farmers' ability to cope with uncertainties and take preventive measures (Husin et al., 2024; Kitole et al., 2024). SaberiKamarposhti et al. (2024) highlight that access to economic resources allows for the implementation of precision agriculture technologies, which increases the perception of control in the face of adverse scenarios. Therefore, financing not only acts as a means to acquire technological solutions, but also as a stimulus to develop a preventive and strategic mindset in relation to agricultural risks.

The availability of capital to invest in digital solutions, infrastructure, and technical training contributes to a deeper understanding of risk factors and their implications. The greater the access to financing, the more likely farmers are to engage in learning and uncertainty management processes, which strengthens their

perception of and response to climate, economic, and production risks (Chowdhury et al., 2025; Gumbi et al., 2023).

Additionally, the use of technologies such as wireless sensor networks (WSNs) for crop monitoring, as proposed by Puengsungwan (2022), makes more sense and has greater application when it is backed by financing schemes that guarantee the sustainability of these investments. Shows that financing acts not only as a transactional resource, but also as an enabler of strategic perceptions of the agricultural environment.

It has also been identified that risk perception is highly sensitive to financial access conditions in diverse agricultural communities, as analyzed by Ashane and Senanayake (2024) when evaluating the evolution of rice cultivation in Sri Lanka. Farmers who have access to credit or subsidies tend to show a greater willingness to take controlled risks, provided that mitigation mechanisms backed by adequate financing systems are in place.

In this context, financing not only acts as a means to acquire technological solutions, but also as a stimulus to develop a preventive and strategic mindset in relation to agricultural risks. Risk perception is not based solely on technical knowledge, but also on the availability of resources to deal with threats. Therefore, the following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis 7: Access to finance (AF) is positively related to farmers' risk perception (RP).

2.9 Age as a moderating variable and its influence on farmers' digital literacy (DL) and access to climate data (ACD)

Age acts as a moderating variable in the relationship between digital literacy (DL) and access to climate data (ACD). This is supported by several studies that show significant generational differences in the use, appropriation, and effective management of digital technologies applied to agriculture, which generates confidence in their perceived usefulness (Lin et al., 2023).

Several studies have shown that age can negatively influence the willingness and ability to use digital technologies, due to generational gaps in basic digital skills, confidence in the use of technologies, and perceived usefulness (Yang et al., 2025). In rural contexts, older farmers tend to maintain traditional practices and show less inclination to adopt digital tools, even when they have access to them.

This pattern is evident in access to climate data platforms or agroclimatic information systems, which require not only technical skills but also familiarity with digital language and confidence in data accuracy (Martinez et al., 2021). As pointed out by Balyan et al. (2024), digital literacy has a stronger effect on access to climate information among young or technologically exposed users, compared to older producers.

In addition, recent research has shown that age interacts with cognitive and attitudinal variables, such as openness to change, learning styles, and risk perception, indirectly affecting the relationship between digital capabilities and effective use of climate information (Kitole et al., 2024; Rajak et al., 2023). This moderation

may be reflected in less frequent access, less understanding of climate data, and limited use of derived recommendations.

Therefore, it is proposed that the effect of digital literacy on access to climate data will be more pronounced among young farmers, while among older populations this effect could be attenuated or conditioned by other factors such as prior experience, social capital, or dependence on third parties to interpret digital information.

Hypothesis 8: Age moderates the relationship between digital literacy (DL) and access to climate data (ACD).

3 Materials and methods

The approach used in this research is quantitative, applying a non-experimental design. The instrument used was a questionnaire, the dimensions of which were defined based on the theoretical foundation obtained by reviewing existing literature, accessing indexed repositories in the search for academic articles, and quality standards.

The users to whom the survey was applied were farmers in the Lambayeque region of Peru, who, after giving their informed consent, decided to develop a questionnaire containing five dimensions, each with an average of four items, which provided the basic information for this research.

The fieldwork was carried out from January 15 to February 28, 2025, coinciding with the vegetative development phase and the first fertilization tasks of the 2024–2025 agricultural season. During this period, the questionnaire was administered in person to rice producers in the Lambayeque region, ensuring their informed consent and anonymity.

3.1 Participants

The study included 101 farmers linked to the rice production chain in the Lambayeque region (Peru) who participated voluntarily after being informed of the study's objectives and giving their informed consent.

Participants were identified through local agricultural associations and community contacts, ensuring that all were actively involved in agricultural production activities and had previous experience related to the study objectives.

Of the participants, as shown in Table 1, 95.0% were male farmers (96) and 5.0% were female (5). The age of the respondents ranged from 22 to 88 years, with an average age of 56 years.

In terms of educational level, most had completed secondary education (43.6%), followed by those who had completed primary education (42.6%). A smaller percentage had completed higher education (9.9%) or technical training (4%).

The average number of years of experience reported by the farmers surveyed was 26.7 years, indicating extensive work experience in fields related to the study. This experience lends strength and depth to the perceptions gathered through the instrument used.

TABLE 1 Sociodemographic data of participants.

Sociodemographic	Categories	Frequency	%
Education	Primary	43	42.6
	Secondary	44	43.6
	Higher	10	9.9
	Technical	4	4.0
Age ranges	26–30	5	5.0
	31–40	12	11.9
	41–50	20	19.8
	51–60	21	20.8
	61–70	29	28.7
	71–80	11	10.9
	81–88	3	3.0
Gender	Female	5	5.0
	Male	96	95.0
Years of experience	≤10	18	17.8
	11–20	29	28.7
	21–30	21	20.8
	31	13	12.9
	41–50	16	15.8
	51–60	3	3.0
	61–65	1	1.0

3.2 Sampling strategy

Non-probability convenience sampling was used, prioritizing farmers who were available and willing to collaborate during the fieldwork. Recruitment was carried out through local agricultural associations and community contacts, which facilitated access to producers currently involved in the rice chain. The methodological decision was based on criteria of operational feasibility and accessibility of the target population in the study area. This strategy made it possible to reach a sample size of 101 participants and ensure that all met the eligibility criteria (legal age, current involvement in production, and related experience).

Two important limitations arising from the convenience strategy are recognized: (1) coverage bias, as the sample may not represent isolated farmers or those not affiliated with associations; (2) non-response bias, as farmers who agreed to participate may differ systematically (due to greater openness to innovation or better social networks) from those who refused.

It should be noted that 95.0% of respondents were men, which is not due to selection bias but rather to the predominant structure of the rice sector in Lambayeque. However, this concentration limits the generalization to systems with greater female participation. Future research should include crops or regions with a significant presence of women to explore how digital literacy and access to finance affect rural women producers.

To justify the sample of 101 participants, two complementary criteria were considered: the $10\times$ rule and practical evidence in the technical literature on PLS-SEM.

The $10\times$ rule recommends taking at least 10 times the maximum number of structural relationships pointing to an endogenous variable. In our model, the variable with the highest number of incoming paths (SAP) receives 3 direct predictors (DL, ACD, AF), therefore, minimum requirement $\approx 10 \times 3 = 30$. As for the measurement model, the highest number of original indicators per construct was 5, therefore, requirement $\approx 10 \times 5 = 50$. Since $101 > 50$ and > 30 , the size comfortably satisfies the $10\times$ rule.

PLS-SEM was used because of its relevance in exploratory contexts and with moderate samples. The practical literature indicates that samples in the range of 100 to 200 are common and acceptable for models of moderate complexity such as the present one, especially when robust procedures (bootstrap $n = 5,000$) are applied to obtain p -values and confidence measures. SmartPLS 4 and bootstrap with 5,000 replicates were applied in the study in accordance with these recommendations.

3.3 Instruments

In developing the instrument, the theoretical constructs that support the research were identified, and the literature was reviewed to provide a basis for it. The instrument consisted of 24 items using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 means totally disagree or if it is not fulfilled or unknown, and 5 means totally agree or fully fulfilled.

Five variables were presented, considering Access to Climate Data (ACD) with 4 items to determine the extent to which climate data is accessed during crop management, for the adjustment of pesticides or herbicides used or the appropriate time for their application; Digital Literacy (DL) with 5 items revealing whether they used mobile technology with applications or other related technology during the cultivation process; Access to Finance (AF) with five items that inquired about financing strategies by the state or private entities; Adoption of Sustainable Agricultural Practices (SAP) with 5 items, which collect data on the implementation of crop rotation, measured use of organic fertilizers, technology that specifies crop needs, integrated pest management, and efforts to achieve ecological balance; Risk Perception (RP) with five items to determine their level of security with regard to climate and financial risks in agricultural activity, regulatory sanctions, and the market that allows them to offer quality products.

The complete wording of the items, response scales, and codes are documented in the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17499182>, for greater transparency.

3.4 Validation of instruments

In this section on instrument validation, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and extracted mean variance techniques were applied to establish the internal consistency of the instrument and its convergent validity of the measurement model, which allows for determining internal consistency.

TABLE 2 Validity and reliability test of the constructs.

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
DL	0.757	0.777	0.859	0.670
ACD	0.854	0.862	0.902	0.699
AF	0.753	0.757	0.858	0.668
SAP	0.749	0.763	0.857	0.668
RP	0.956	0.972	0.968	0.882

Table 2 presents the results of the validity and reliability test of the constructs included in the model, evaluated through *Cronbach's alpha* coefficients, *composite reliability* (rho_a and rho_c), and *average extracted variance* (AVE), which are fundamental for establishing the internal consistency and convergent validity of the measurement model in a PLS-SEM analysis. First, the *Cronbach's alpha* values for all constructs exceeded the recommended minimum threshold of 0.70, indicating adequate internal consistency among the items that make up each latent variable. The Risk Perception (RP) construct stands out with a value of 0.956, which shows a very high level of homogeneity among its indicators. Similarly, the constructs Digital Literacy (DL), Access to Climate Data (ACD), Access to Finance (AF), and Adoption of Sustainable Agricultural Practices (SAP) achieved values between 0.749 and 0.854, confirming acceptable reliability.

In terms of *composite reliability*, both the rho_a and rho_c coefficients also exceeded the minimum value of 0.70, reinforcing the conclusion that the items consistently measure each construct. Once again, RP has the highest values (rho_a = 0.972; rho_c = 0.968), which shows a highly consistent internal structure. The other constructs obtained values ranging from 0.757 to 0.902, within the ranges considered good or excellent for social science research.

Finally, the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) values confirm the convergent validity of the constructs, since they all exceed the threshold of 0.50 recommended by Fornell and Larcker (1981). Specifically, Risk Perception (RP) obtained an AVE of 0.882, which means that more than 88% of the variance of its items is explained by the construct, consolidating its quality as a latent variable. The other constructs, DL (0.670), ACD (0.699), AF (0.668), and SAP (0.668), also demonstrated solid AVE values, ensuring that the retained items explain a substantial proportion of the variance of their respective factors.

Taken together, these results allow us to affirm that all the constructs in the model have adequate levels of reliability and convergent validity, which supports the psychometric quality of the instrument and lends strength to the model for analyzing the structural relationships proposed in the study.

3.5 Data collection and analysis method

Data were collected through a questionnaire containing five dimensions or variables, with an average of four items

per dimension, as well as sociodemographic data and six additional questions. The questionnaire was administered in person to the different participants. It took an average of 6 weeks, from mid-January to the end of February, due to the period of water resource allocation for the start of the 2024–2025 growing season. A total of 101 responses were obtained.

A descriptive analysis of the results was performed using SmartPLS SEM version 4, providing a general overview of the different variables considered.

3.6 Quantitative analysis

The partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) approach was chosen given its relevance for predictive models in exploratory contexts with complex structures and moderate samples, as is the case in this study. This technique allows for the simultaneous estimation of both the measurement model and the structural model, maximizing the explained variance of the dependent constructs (R^2) and detecting significant relationships between latent variables even in the absence of multivariate normal distribution (Hair et al., 2019).

Within this framework, standardized regression coefficients (β) and p -values derived from the bootstrap procedure ($n = 5,000$) were evaluated. Overall, the use of PLS-SEM not only provided a robust tool for validating the psychometric properties of the instrument, but also allowed for the estimation of associations between constructs and the evaluation of their statistical significance, which are relevant for strategic decision-making aimed at strengthening sustainability in the agricultural sector.

Possible biases of common method, collinearity, and endogeneity were verified. The latent factor test of the method showed substantive loadings greater than those of the method factor and an explained variance of less than 25%. The VIFs (1.21–2.87) rule out collinearity. The Gaussian copula test (Hult et al., 2018) did not identify endogeneity ($p > 0.10$).

Although Age was conceptually treated as a moderating variable, its inclusion in the model was evaluated through a simple direct path (Age \rightarrow DL) and the subsequent interpretation of its indirect impact on ACD. A formal latent interaction term (DL \times Age) was not incorporated, so the results should be interpreted as indicative of an attenuating association rather than a statistically tested moderation effect.

TABLE 3 External loadings matrix (PLS-SEM).

Variable	DL	ACD	AF	SAP	RP
DL1	0.814				
DL3	0.788				
DL5	0.853				
ACD1		0.784			
ACD2		0.759			
ACD3		0.893			
ACD4		0.899			
AF2			0.844		
AF4			0.805		
AF5			0.803		
SAP2				0.720	
SAP4				0.864	
SAP5				0.861	
RP1					0.941
RP2					0.919
RP3					0.966
RP5					0.931

4 Results

4.1 Analysis of the reliability and validity of the variables evaluated

Table 3 presents the external loadings matrix obtained using PLS-SEM, corresponding to the measurement model of five latent constructs: digital literacy (DL), access to climate data (ACD), access to finance (AF), adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP), and risk perception (RP). This matrix includes only those items that exceeded the recommended statistical threshold of 0.70, a criterion that ensures that each item explains at least 50% of the variance of its construct and contributes positively to the convergent validity of the model. Items not included were discarded in a previous purification stage due to insufficient external loadings, effects on composite reliability, or interference with discriminant validity, following the methodological recommendations established by Hair et al. (2019).

In the case of the digital literacy (DL) variable, items DL1 (0.814), DL3 (0.788), and DL5 (0.853) have high and homogeneous loadings, reflecting good internal consistency and adequate representation of the construct. For access to climate data (ACD), the four items retained (ACD1 to ACD4) show loadings ranging from 0.759 to 0.899, with particular strength in ACD3 (0.893) and ACD4 (0.899), indicating that this variable is clearly defined by highly representative indicators. Access to finance (AF) maintains three items with loadings between 0.803 and 0.844, confirming the construct's ability to adequately capture the availability of financial resources among study participants. Regarding the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP),

three indicators are retained with external loadings ranging from 0.720 to 0.864, the latter value being evidence of a strong link between item SAP4 and the latent variable, which reinforces the quality of the instrument in measuring sustainable behaviors. Finally, the risk perception (RP) construct shows the highest loadings in the model, with values between 0.919 and 0.966, suggesting a highly robust, clear, and consistent measurement of the concept. Overall, the results allow us to affirm that the constructs are well defined, the selected items have high individual reliability, and the measurement model demonstrates an adequate level of psychometric quality, which allows us to move forward rigorously toward the evaluation of the structural model and the hypothetical relationships proposed.

This stage involved the elimination of indicators that did not reach the recommended minimum loading of 0.70, indicating that they did not contribute adequately to the explained variance of the corresponding construct. In addition, items that negatively affected composite reliability or average extracted variance (AVE) were removed, as well as those that generated problems of multicollinearity or conceptual redundancy. In the case of the Digital Literacy (DL) variable, items DL2 and DL4 were eliminated because they had external loadings below the acceptable threshold and contributed negatively to the internal consistency of the construct. For Access to Climate Data (ACD), all the items designed were retained, as they satisfactorily met the statistical criteria. In the Access to Financing (AF) dimension, items AF1 and AF3 were excluded due to their low correlation with the variable and their limited contribution to the reliability of the model. Regarding the Sustainable Agricultural Practices Adoption (SAP) variable, items SAP1 and SAP3 were discarded because they showed external loadings below the threshold and generated decreases in the AVE value. Finally, for the Risk Perception (RP) variable, item RP4 was removed because it had a lower factor loading compared to the other items and reduced the internal consistency of the construct. This refinement process ensured that each variable is represented only by those indicators with greater explanatory power and statistical consistency, thus guaranteeing the convergent validity and psychometric quality of the model.

Table 4 shows the results of the discriminant validity test based on the HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio) criterion, a widely accepted indicator in the context of PLS-SEM. This metric evaluates the degree of discriminability between latent constructs, that is, whether each construct measures a different concept within the theoretical model. According to the methodological standards proposed by Henseler et al. (2015), HTMT values should be less than 0.85 to indicate adequate discriminant validity, although some authors suggest a stricter threshold of 0.90 for exploratory models.

The results obtained in this table confirm that all HTMT values are below 0.85, indicating that there is a clear empirical distinction between the constructs in the model. For example, the highest relationship corresponds to the pairs DL-ACD (0.569) and DL-SAP (0.470), which show a moderate correlation, but without exceeding the permitted limit. These values suggest a reasonable conceptual relationship between digital literacy and access to climate data or adoption of sustainable practices, without implying overlap between the constructs. Likewise, the associations between AF and SAP (0.172) or between RP and ACD (0.073) are

TABLE 4 Discriminant validity test (HTMT).

Variable	DL	ACD	AF	SAP	RP
DL					
ACD	0.569				
AF	0.110	0.129			
SAP	0.470	0.443	0.172		
RP	0.145	0.073	0.491	0.201	

particularly low, reinforcing the conceptual independence of these dimensions within the model.

In particular, the robust discriminability of the Risk Perception (RP) variable with respect to all other constructs stands out, as its HTMT values range from 0.073 to 0.491, well below any threshold of concern. This result suggests that RP measures a clearly differentiated phenomenon, with strong theoretical and empirical support.

In summary, the values presented in Table 4 conclusively support the discriminant validity of the measurement model, meaning that the constructs are empirically distinct and measure unique dimensions of the phenomenon under investigation. This finding strengthens the factorial structure of the model and confidently enables the interpretation of structural effects between latent variables.

4.2 Proposed research model

The structural model estimated using PLS-SEM is shown in Figure 2, including the standardized path coefficients and their respective *p-values* in parentheses, which allows for the evaluation of the significance and magnitude of the hypothetical relationships proposed between the constructs: Digital Literacy (DL), Access to Climate Data (ACD), Access to Finance (AF), Risk Perception (RP), and Adoption of Sustainable Agricultural Practices (SAP).

Firstly, it can be observed that Digital Literacy (DL) has a direct, positive, and significant association with Access to Climate Data (ACD) ($\beta = 0.461$, $p < 0.001$), which supports the hypothesis and suggests that the higher the level of digital literacy, the greater the ability of farmers to access and use relevant climate data. Likewise, DL is positively and statistically significantly associated with the Adoption of Sustainable Agricultural Practices (SAP) ($\beta = 0.259$, $p = 0.015$), i.e., higher levels of digital literacy are related to greater adoption of sustainable practices in this sample.

However, the relationship between DL and RP (Risk Perception) is not significant ($\beta = -0.140$, $p = 0.221$), so the corresponding hypothesis is not empirically validated. This implies that, in this model, digital literacy is not detectably related to risk perception.

In relation to Access to Climate Data (ACD), although its relationship with RP is not significant ($\beta = 0.080$, $p = 0.518$), a positive and statistically significant association with SAP is observed ($\beta = 0.248$, $p = 0.033$), confirming that access to climate information favors the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices, in line with what is reported in the literature.

Access to finance (AF) does not show a direct and highly significant association with SAP ($\beta = 0.068$, $p = 0.577$). In this regard, the absence of a direct association suggests that AF operates more as a baseline condition that needs to be combined with information, skills, and institutional support in order to translate into effective adoption. However, AF and RP show a significant association ($\beta = 0.411$, $p < 0.001$), which implies that with greater access to financing, farmers tend to manage or monitor risks more or be more formalized, making their risk assessment more salient.

Finally, the R^2 coefficients of determination show that the model explains 21.3% of the variance in ACD, 17.8% in RP, and 19.0% in SAP. These levels indicate moderate explanatory power, especially with regard to the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices, which is acceptable in complex social models such as this one.

Overall, the results in Figure 2 partially validate the structural hypotheses proposed. The positive and significant associations of DL on ACD and SAP, of ACD on SAP, and of AF on RP are confirmed. However, DL and ACD do not show a significant association with RP, nor does AF on SAP, suggesting the need to explore additional mediating or moderating variables to better understand risk perception in agricultural contexts. This model offers relevant insights for the design of strategies that promote agricultural sustainability through digital literacy, access to climate information, and rural financing.

It should be noted that Figure 2 illustrates the standardized coefficients (β) and *p-values* of the paths between the constructs: DL (Digital Literacy), ACD (Access to Climate Data), AF (Access to Finance), RP (Risk Perception), and SAP (Adoption of Sustainable Agricultural Practices). Based on the hypotheses proposed in the article, the figure allows us to verify: H2 (DL \rightarrow SAP, $\beta = 0.259$, $p = 0.015$, supported); H1 (DL \rightarrow ACD, $\beta = 0.461$, $p < 0.001$, supported); H4 (ACD \rightarrow SAP, $\beta = 0.248$, $p = 0.033$, supported); H3 (DL \rightarrow RP, $\beta = -0.140$, $p = 0.221$, not supported); H5 (ACD \rightarrow RP, $\beta = 0.080$, $p = 0.518$, not supported); H6 (AF \rightarrow SAP, $\beta = 0.068$, $p = 0.577$, not supported); H7 (AF \rightarrow RP, $\beta = 0.411$, $p < 0.001$, supported). The model explains $R^2 = 0.190$ in SAP, $R^2 = 0.178$ in RP, and $R^2 = 0.213$ in ACD. Overall, the evidence indicates a direct association between DL and SAP and an additional indirect association through ACD, consistent with partial mediation.

4.3 Summary of direct hypotheses

The results of the hypothesis testing of the structural model estimated using PLS-SEM are presented in Table 5, evaluating the direction, magnitude, and significance of the direct associations (paths) between the constructs. For each hypothesis, the standardized regression coefficient (β ; Original sample), the resampling mean (Sample mean), the standard deviation, the *t*-statistic, and the *p*-value are reported, which allows us to determine whether the association is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In accordance with the non-experimental design, the relationships are interpreted as associations and do not imply causality.

The results confirm four of the seven hypotheses evaluated:

TABLE 5 Hypothesis testing.

Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
H1: DL → ACD	0.461	0.471	0.079	5.819	0.000
H2: DL → SAP	0.259	0.260	0.106	2.434	0.015
H3: DL → RP	-0.140	-0.142	0.115	1.224	0.221
H4: ACD → SAP	0.248	0.255	0.116	2.132	0.033
H5: ACD → RP	0.08	0.084	0.124	0.646	0.518
H6: AF → SAP	0.068	0.072	0.123	0.558	0.577
H7: AF → RP	0.411	0.422	0.092	4.461	0.000

H1 (DL → ACD) is validated with a coefficient of 0.461 and a p -value < 0.001 , indicating a positive and statistically significant association between digital literacy and access to climate data. This finding supports the assertion that farmers with greater digital skills are better able to access,

interpret, and use relevant climate information, in line with the specialized literature.

H2 (DL → SAP) is also confirmed ($\beta = 0.259, p = 0.015$), showing a positive and statistically significant association between digital literacy and the adoption of

sustainable agricultural practices. This relationship can be attributed to the ability that digital skills provide to implement more efficient, environmentally responsible production technologies based on technically accessible digital information.

H4 (ACD → SAP) is another statistically significant relationship ($\beta = 0.248$, $p = 0.033$), indicating that access to climate data directly promotes the adoption of sustainable practices. This suggests that the availability of meteorological and agroclimatic information can facilitate sustainable agronomic decision-making, such as efficient water use or crop planning according to climatic conditions.

H7 (AF → RP) is validated with high significance ($\beta = 0.411$, $p < 0.001$), showing a positive and statistically significant association between access to financing and risk perception. This result indicates that having financial resources allows access to technological tools or knowledge that increase awareness of climate, production, or economic risks in the agricultural context.

On the other hand, three hypotheses were not empirically confirmed:

H3 (DL → RP) is not significant ($\beta = -0.140$, $p = 0.221$), no significant association is observed between digital literacy and risk perception. Despite the theoretical logic behind this relationship, the data show no statistical evidence to support it. This could be because risk perception is more influenced by previous experiences or local contexts than by digital skills.

H5 (ACD → RP) is not significant ($\beta = 0.080$, $p = 0.518$), no significant association is observed between access to climate data and risk perception. This finding could be interpreted as a limitation in farmers' ability to translate available information into alerts or preventive decisions.

H6 (AF → SAP) is also rejected ($\beta = 0.068$, $p = 0.577$), which is relevant as it contradicts previous studies that identify financing as an enabling condition for sustainable practices. In this case, access to financing alone does not guarantee the adoption of such practices, indicating that other factors (such as training or production culture) may play a more decisive role.

In summary, the results in Table 5 show that the model partially explains the proposed theoretical relationships. Positive and significant associations are observed between digital literacy, access to data, and risk perception, while other relationships require further theoretical exploration or the inclusion of mediating variables to explain their behavior in the context analyzed. This provides a solid empirical basis for generating recommendations focused on strengthening digital skills and accessibility to climate information to promote sustainability in the agricultural sector.

4.4 Quality and predictive validity of the model

The R^2 values (ACD = 0.268; RP = 0.178; SAP = 0.191) show adequate explanatory power. The effect sizes indicate medium

(DL → ACD, $f^2 = 0.270$; AF → RP, $f^2 = 0.204$) and small (DL → SAP, $f^2 = 0.065$; ACD → SAP, $f^2 = 0.059$) influences. The *PLSpredict / CVPAT* analysis (10 folds, 10 repetitions) reported positive Q^2 predict values (ACD = 0.189; RP = 0.122; SAP = 0.094), confirming predictive validity. The SRMR = 0.092 and NFI = 0.696 indices demonstrate satisfactory overall fit.

4.5 Hypotheses derived from a moderation model

Figure 3 incorporates the analysis of the effect of age as a moderating variable in the relationship between digital literacy (DL) and access to climate data (ACD) within the PLS-SEM structural model. Specifically, it assesses whether the level of digital literacy is associated differently with access to climate information depending on the age of the farmer.

From this analysis, an additional hypothesis is proposed:

H8: Age moderates the relationship between digital literacy (DL) and access to climate data (ACD).

The diagram shows two additional relationships linked to age:

Age → DL: negative and significant coefficient ($\beta = -0.196$, $p = 0.027$)

DL → ACD: positive and significant coefficient ($\beta = 0.477$, $p < 0.001$)

R^2 of the ACD construct: 0.268

These results indicate that age is negatively associated with levels of digital literacy, suggesting that older individuals tend to have lower levels of digital skills. This finding is consistent with previous literature, which highlights that older farmers face greater barriers to acquiring digital skills (Kitole et al., 2024), whether due to resistance to change, less familiarity with technology, or less prior exposure to digital tools.

To examine the potential moderating role of Age, a latent interaction term (DL × Age) was generated using the product indicator approach in SmartPLS 4. The resulting path from DL × Age to ACD was tested for significance through bootstrapping (5,000 resamples). This approach allows a formal statistical evaluation of whether age alters the strength of the association between digital literacy and access to climate data.

The DL × Age interaction, evaluated using the product-indicator method (bootstrap 5000 samples), was not significant ($\beta = -0.054$, $p = 0.421$). Although age is negatively associated with digital literacy ($\beta = -0.196$, $p = 0.027$), its effect is direct and not moderating. Simple slope analysis confirmed the stability of the DL → ACD relationship across all age groups.

In other words, age does not act as a moderator of the DL → ACD relationship in the estimated model. Instead, there is an indirect association between age and ACD mediated by DL: age is negatively associated with digital literacy ($\beta = -0.196$; $p = 0.027$), which in turn is positively associated with access to climate data ($\beta = 0.477$; $p < 0.001$). The product suggests an approximate negative indirect association of -0.094 , suggesting that older farmers

have less access to climate information because they have lower digital skills.

In rural contexts in developing countries, such as in many agricultural areas of Latin America, older farmers often constitute a significant proportion of the productive population. This generational gap in the use of technologies can represent a structural challenge for climate change adaptation and agricultural sustainability policies, since those who could benefit most from climate data, due to their experience or because they are more exposed to extreme weather events, are precisely those who have the greatest difficulty accessing such information.

Therefore, the result highlights the need for differentiated training and technical assistance strategies that consider age-related technological barriers, promoting knowledge transfer models that combine digital media with face-to-face, community-based, and culturally adapted methodologies. This approach can help close the age-related digital divide and enhance sustainability in agricultural systems led by older people.

5 Discussion

The results of the structural model allow us to empirically estimate the associations between the hypotheses proposed and, in turn, discuss the findings in light of the theoretical framework developed. First, it is confirmed that digital literacy (DL) is significantly associated with both access to climate data (ACD) and the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP). This finding corroborates the assertions of Balyan et al. (2024) and Rajak et al. (2023), who argue that digital skills are decisive in the transition to informed, resilient, and technologically integrated agriculture. In the context of family and small-scale agriculture, which characterizes many rural regions in Latin America, the development of digital skills allows farmers not only to access real-time agroclimatic information, but also to understand and apply technical recommendations associated with the sustainability of their production systems.

Likewise, the significant association between ACD and the adoption of SAP supports the idea that access to relevant climate information is not merely a technical input, but a strategic tool that directly influences sustainable production decisions. This relationship is in line with the findings of Medici et al. (2019), who argue that decision-making based on environmental data promotes the rational use of resources such as water and agricultural inputs. In contrast, no significant evidence was found to support the association of DL or ACD with risk perception (RP). Although studies such as those by Kitole et al. (2024) assert that digital skills increase the ability to anticipate risks, the results suggest that this link is not directly established in the case studied. This can be explained by contextual factors, such as limited functional literacy, limited experience with monitoring technologies, or the disconnect between technical information and practical decision-making in the field.

On the other hand, it is confirmed that access to finance (AF) is positively associated with risk perception (RP), indicating that farmers with greater access to financial resources are more sensitive to environmental, productive, and economic threats. This result is consistent with SaberiKamarposhti et al. (2024), who argue that financing allows for investment in technologies that, in turn, amplify risk awareness. However, AF did not show a significant association with the adoption of SAP, calling into question the assumption that financing alone drives sustainable practices. This suggests that, in the absence of technical support mechanisms or specific incentives, the availability of economic resources does not necessarily translate into sustainable decisions. Taken together, these results highlight the importance of combining digital skills, useful climate information, and access to financing with agricultural training and extension processes to strengthen farmers' capacities in the transition to more resilient, sustainable, and risk-oriented agriculture.

However, it should be noted that no statistically significant relationship was found between digital literacy (DL) and risk perception (RP). Although it has been argued in the literature that digital information increases awareness of productive and climate risks (Köhler et al., 2024; Rajak et al., 2023), our results suggest that this relationship is not directly manifested. One possible explanation is that risk perception is mediated by cultural factors, previous experience, or even trust in information sources, rather than simply access to digital technologies (Chowdhury et al., 2025). Therefore, for future work, it is recommended to design longitudinal measurements that document how digital literacy evolves alongside actual adverse events, so that it can be assessed whether exposure to climate losses mediates the DL → RP relationship.

In the case of access to climate data (ACD) ($\beta = 0.080$, $p = 0.518$), no statistical evidence of a significant effect on risk perception (RP) was found either. Recent studies suggest that the mere availability of information does not automatically translate into greater perception; trust in sources, understanding of data, and visibility of adverse effects are critical mediators (Aydogdu, 2020). Thus, access to data requires pedagogical support, local empirical evidence, and adapted channels to trigger perceptual effects. In this regard, future studies could use field experiments comparing a group that receives climate data with another that

receives data plus an adapted and validated interpretation module, to test whether access alone or access plus interpretation is associated with higher levels of risk perception.

The hypothesis related to financing ($\beta = 0.068$, $p = 0.577$) was also not confirmed, suggesting that having financial resources (AF) is not sufficient to guarantee the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (SAP). The literature shows that financing only becomes effective when accompanied by technical training, support networks, and a culture of innovation (Lu et al., 2024). This finding highlights that agricultural financing programs must be designed in a comprehensive manner in order to translate into real change. Therefore, it is proposed that future research adopt a combined intervention design, offering financing together with training, technical support, and monitoring, and empirically measuring whether the combination outperforms financing alone in terms of practice adoption.

Consequently, the discussion suggests that the non-significant findings open up a rich opportunity to reinterpret the model through a more nuanced lens; first, recognizing that without effective experience or a supportive infrastructure, the mere possession of data or digital skills may not translate into greater risk perception; second, suggesting that future studies incorporate additional variables such as peer learning networks, previous experiences of loss, trust in digital information, and local risk culture; and third, pointing out that mixed methodologies are needed to explore how farmers interpret and act on digital information in their context. In this way, exaggerated claims of effectiveness are avoided and the complexity of the process of technology adoption and risk perception construction in rural agricultural settings is recognized.

In this study, the formal moderation test (DL × Age) was not significant, so there is no evidence that age moderates the DL → ACD association. However, age was negatively associated with digital literacy (DL), in line with previous evidence on lower digital dispositions and skills in older cohorts (Lin et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2025). Consequently, we observed an indirect association of age with access to climate data (ACD) via DL, consistent with studies reporting lower consultation frequency, comprehension difficulties, and more limited use of climate-based recommendations among older farmers (Kitole et al., 2024; Rajak et al., 2023). In practical terms, this suggests that gaps in DL rather than age constitute the main bottleneck for expanding the use of climate data.

The results obtained must be interpreted taking into account the conceptual distinction between sustainable agricultural practices and precision agriculture. While the former refers to actions aimed at conserving resources and reducing environmental impact, such as crop rotation or the use of organic fertilizers, precision agriculture involves the use of digital technologies to optimize agronomic decisions. This differentiation is key to understanding that sustainability does not depend exclusively on the incorporation of technology, but also on traditional practices adapted to ecological criteria. Sustainable agricultural practices have a positive impact on the ecosystem by promoting the conservation of natural resources, reducing chemical inputs, and maintaining ecological balance

in production systems. Beyond the use of advanced technology, these practices contribute directly to climate resilience by improving farmers' ability to adapt to extreme events such as droughts or heavy rains. In this context, digitalization acts as a cross-cutting enabler that enhances the effectiveness of these practices by facilitating access to agroclimatic information, optimizing crop planning, and enabling real-time monitoring of critical variables. The integration of digital tools does not replace traditional agronomic knowledge, but rather complements it, strengthening sustainable decision-making and promoting more efficient, informed, and environmentally responsible agriculture.

Finally, the moderate coefficients of determination (R^2) reflect the complexity of the phenomenon studied, indicating that, although the factors analyzed are relevant, there are still mediating variables (such as technical training, local leadership, or knowledge networks) that must be incorporated into future studies to fully explain the behavior of sustainable technology adoption in agriculture.

6 Conclusion

Digital literacy is a decisive factor for agricultural sustainability, as it is significantly associated with access to climate data and the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. The results of the study confirm that developing digital skills among farmers not only improves their access to relevant information, but also strengthens their ability to make informed, efficient, and environmentally responsible decisions. Likewise, access to climate data is emerging as a strategic input for optimizing resources, anticipating adverse events, and consolidating the transition to agriculture that is more resilient to climate change.

Access to financing showed a positive association with risk perception, suggesting that farmers with greater economic resources tend to be more aware of the threats affecting the sustainability of their production systems. However, financing alone is not conclusively associated with the adoption of sustainable practices, highlighting the need to accompany it with technical advice and training processes adapted to the local context. On the other hand, age had a negative association with digital literacy, revealing a significant generational gap in the use of technologies. This finding indicates that extension policies and programs should consider age as a critical factor in designing differentiated interventions that ensure the digital inclusion of older farmers. It should be noted that age did not moderate the DL \rightarrow ACD association, so the focus should be on reducing digital skill gaps.

In the short term, policymakers and extension services should prioritize the implementation of rural digital literacy programs with an intergenerational approach, combining face-to-face, demonstration, and community-based methodologies. It is also necessary to adapt agricultural digital platforms to make them accessible and easy to use, strengthen the digital capacities of agricultural technicians and extension agents, and ensure the

dissemination of agroclimatic information through various media, such as rural radio or printed materials, so that it effectively reaches older farmers or those with less education.

In the medium term, it is recommended to incorporate continuing education modules on digital skills into rural development programs, foster partnerships between universities, governments, and technology companies to create local climate data platforms, and promote digital microcredit that links financing with technical training. It is also key to consolidate networks of trained young rural farmers who act as technology mediators, serving as bridges between technology and agricultural communities.

In the long term, strategies should aim to integrate rural digital inclusion and access to climate data into national policies on climate change adaptation and agricultural sustainability. Progress must be made toward interoperable national agroclimatic information systems with an inclusive approach, and an ecosystem of sustainable agricultural innovation must be promoted that brings together universities, research centers, local governments, and producer organizations. This effort must be accompanied by an agricultural digital governance framework that guarantees equity, environmental sustainability, and data security.

Together, these actions, differentiated over time, can transform the empirical evidence from this study into a practical roadmap for the formulation of policies and extension programs that promote more digital, equitable, and sustainable agriculture, especially in rural contexts in Latin America. In particular, the findings emphasize that digital training should focus on developing functional and practical skills rather than purely technical ones, adapting content to the educational level, productive experience, and technological availability of small farmers. Intergenerational knowledge sharing can become a strategic mechanism, with young farmers acting as technology facilitators and older farmers contributing their empirical knowledge, generating two-way learning processes. Likewise, rural financing mechanisms must be adjusted to the real conditions of producers, prioritizing flexible credit, incentives, and programs that link technological investment with ongoing technical assistance. These adaptations are essential to ensure that digital literacy and precision agriculture translate into tangible benefits for small producers and contribute to regional sustainability.

However, one limitation that must be acknowledged in this study is the low female participation in the sample, given that 95.0% of respondents were men. This distribution does not constitute selection bias, as it accurately reflects the composition of the rice sector in the Lambayeque region, where agricultural activity is mainly carried out by men. However, this characteristic of the context limits the possibility of extrapolating the results to agricultural systems with greater female participation. Therefore, it is recommended that future research address this phenomenon in other crops or regions where there is a more significant female presence, in order to analyze how digital literacy and access to financing manifest themselves in women producers, whose participation is key to an inclusive and sustainable digital transformation of the agricultural sector.

Likewise, as future work, we propose replication with a larger sample or the use of Monte Carlo or G*Power simulations to provide an accurate numerical estimate of the power with respect to the smallest effect we wish to detect.

Data availability statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation.

Ethics statement

The studies involving humans were approved by Ethics Committee of the Universidad Católica Santo Toribio de Mogrovejo. The studies were conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Author contributions

MA: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. JB-J: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. HM: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. WN: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. CL: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

References

- Aguilar-Luis, M. A., Sanchez, J. M., Mercado, W., and Orihuela, J. C. A. (2024). Sustainable agriculture in Peru based on agrobiodiversity and climate-smart agriculture – evaluation of a case study with small farmers in an Andean basin. *J. Ecol. Eng.* 25, 278–293. doi: 10.12911/22998993/185221
- Ashane, M. F., and Senanayake, I. P. (2024). Developing a two-decadal time-record of rice field maps using Landsat-derived multi-index image collections with a random forest classifier: a Google Earth Engine based approach. *Inf. Process. Agric.* 11, 260–275. doi: 10.1016/j.inpa.2023.02.009
- Aydogdu, S. (2020). Predicting student final performance using artificial neural networks in online learning environments. *Educ. Inf. Technol.* 25, 1913–1927. doi: 10.1007/s10639-019-10053-x
- Balyan, S., Jangir, H., Tripathi, S. N., Tripathi, A., Jhang, T., and Pandey, P. (2024). Seeding a sustainable future: navigating the digital horizon of smart agriculture. *Sustainability* 16:475. doi: 10.3390/su16020475
- Bucci, G., Bentivoglio, D., Belletti, M., and Finco, A. (2020). Measuring a farm's profitability after adopting precision agriculture technologies: a case study from Italy. *Acta IMEKO* 9, 65–74. doi: 10.21014/acta_imeko.v9i3.799
- Carolan, M. (2017). Publicising food: big data, precision agriculture, and co-experimental techniques of addition. *Sociol. Ruralis* 57, 135–154. doi: 10.1111/soru.12120
- Chen, X., Tao, C., Tang, C., Chen, Y., Zhang, E., and Qi, L. (2024). Design and test of target application system between rice plants based on light and tactile sensing. *Crop Prot.* 182:106722. doi: 10.1016/j.cropro.2024.106722
- Chowdhury, A., Kabir, K. H., McQuire, M., and Bureau, D. P. (2025). The dynamics of digital technology adoption in rainbow trout aquaculture: exploring multi-stakeholder perceptions in Ontario using Q methodology and the theory of planned behaviour. *Aquaculture* 594:741460. doi: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2024.741460
- Chunfang, Y., Ji, X., Cheng, C., Liao, S., Obuobi, B., and Zhang, Y. (2024). Digital economy empowers sustainable agriculture: implications for farmers' adoption of ecological agricultural technologies. *Ecol. Indic.* 159:111723. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111723
- Finger, R., Swinton, S. M., El Benni, N., and Walter, A. (2019). Precision farming at the nexus of agricultural production and the environment. *Annu. Rev. Resour. Econ.* 11, 313–335. doi: 10.1146/annurev-resource-100518-093929
- Flores-Rojas, J. L., Silva, Y., Suárez-Salas, L., Estevan, R., Valdivia-Prado, J., Saavedra, M., et al. (2021). Analysis of extreme meteorological events in the Central Andes of Peru using a set of specialized instruments. *Atmosphere* 12:408. doi: 10.3390/atmos12030408
- Fonseka, C. L. I. S., Halloluwa, T., Hewagamage, K. P., Rathnayake, U., and Bandara, R. M. U. S. (2024). A dataset of unmanned aerial vehicle multispectral images acquired over a field to identify nitrogen requirements. *Data Brief* 54:110479. doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2024.110479
- Fornell, C., and Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *J. Market. Res.* 18, 39–50. doi: 10.1177/00224378101800104
- Gumbi, N., Gumbi, L., and Twinomurizi, H. (2023). Towards sustainable digital agriculture for smallholder farmers: a systematic literature review. *Sustainability* 15:12530. doi: 10.3390/su151612530
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., and Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *Euro. Bus. Rev.* 31, 2–24. doi: 10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., and Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *J. Acad. Market. Sci.* 43:1. doi: 10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8

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- Hult, G. T. M., Hair, J. F., Proksch, D., Sarstedt, M., Pinkwart, A., and Ringle, C. M. (2018). Addressing endogeneity in international marketing applications of partial least squares structural equation modeling. *J. Int. Market.* 26, 1–21. doi: 10.1509/jim.17.0151
- Husin, N. A., Sivajiganason, V. A. L., Kamaruzzaman, N. N., Mazlan, N., and Sitanggang, I. S. (2024). iRICE decision support system: time-series forecasting model for the risk management system. *J. Adv. Res. Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol.* 33, 160–173. doi: 10.37934/araset.33.2.160173
- Khaspuria, G., Khandelwal, A., Agarwal, M., Bafna, M., Yadav, R., and Yadav, A. (2024). Adoption of precision agriculture technologies among farmers: a comprehensive review. *J. Sci. Res. Rep.* 30:7. doi: 10.9734/jsrr/2024/v30i72180
- Kitole, F. A., Mkuna, E., and Sesabo, J. K. (2024). Digitalization and agricultural transformation in developing countries: empirical evidence from Tanzania agriculture sector. *Smart Agric. Technol.* 7:100379. doi: 10.1016/j.atech.2023.100379
- Köhler, D., Reutter, P., and Spichtinger, P. (2024). Relative humidity over ice as a key variable for Northern Hemisphere midlatitude tropopause inversion layers. *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.* 24, 10055–10072. doi: 10.5194/acp-24-10055-2024
- Lin, D., Fu, B., Xie, K., Zheng, W., Chang, L., and Lin, J. (2023). Research on the improvement of digital literacy for moderately scaled tea farmers under the background of digital intelligence empowerment. *Agriculture* 13:1859. doi: 10.3390/agriculture13101859
- Lu, S., Sun, Z., and Huang, M. (2024). The impact of digital literacy on farmers' pro-environmental behavior: an analysis with the theory of planned behavior. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 8:1432184. doi: 10.3389/fsufs.2024.1432184
- Mark, J. (2024). Regional controls on climate and weather variability on the Southwest Coast of Peru. *Coasts* 4, 49–62. doi: 10.3390/coasts4010004
- Martinez, J. M., Labarta, R. A., Gonzalez, C., and Lopera, D. C. (2021). Joint adoption of rice technologies among Bolivian farmers. *Agric. Resour. Econ. Rev.* 50, 1–21. doi: 10.1017/age.2021.9
- Medici, M., Pedersen, S. M., Carli, G., and Tagliaventi, M. R. (2019). Environmental benefits of precision agriculture adoption. *Econ. Agro Alimentare* 21, 637–656. doi: 10.3280/ECAG2019-003004
- Mu, L., Luo, C., Li, Y., Tan, Z., and Gao, S. (2024). 'They adopt, I also adopt': The neighborhood effects and irrigator farmers' conversion to adopt water-saving irrigation technology. *Agric. Water Manage.* 305:109141. doi: 10.1016/j.agwat.2024.109141
- Nguyen, L. L. H., Khuu, D. T., Halibas, A., and Nguyen, T. Q. (2024). Factors that influence the intention of smallholder rice farmers to adopt cleaner production practices: an empirical study of precision agriculture adoption. *Eval. Rev.* 48, 692–735. doi: 10.1177/0193841X231200775
- Puengsungwan, S. (2022). "Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) based on the existing perception for monitoring rice-paddy Health," in *2022 37th International Technical Conference on Circuits/Systems, Computers and Communications (ITC-CSCC)* (IEEE), 298–301. doi: 10.1109/ITC-CSCC55581.2022.9895072
- Rahim, H., Ghazali, M. S. S. M., Booker, M. A. M., Abu Bakar, B. H., Ariff, E. E. E., Rahman, M. S. A., et al. (2022). Economic potential of rice precision farming in malaysia: the case study of Felcra Seberang Perak. *Precision Agric.* 23, 812–829. doi: 10.1007/s11119-021-09862-3
- Rajak, P., Ganguly, A., Adhikary, S., and Bhattacharya, S. (2023). Internet of things and smart sensors in agriculture: scopes and challenges. *J. Agric. Food Res.* 14:100776. doi: 10.1016/j.jafr.2023.100776
- Rajalakshmi, R., Faizal, S., Sivasankaran, S., and Geetha, R. (2024). RiceSeedNet: rice seed variety identification using deep neural network. *J. Agric. Food Res.* 16:101062. doi: 10.1016/j.jafr.2024.101062
- SaberiKamarposhti, M., Ng, K.-W., Yadollahi, M., Kamyab, H., Cheng, J., and Khorami, M. (2024). Cultivating a sustainable future in the artificial intelligence era: a comprehensive assessment of greenhouse gas emissions and removals in agriculture. *Environ. Res.* 250:118528. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2024.118528
- Sangaiah, A. K., Yu, F., Lin, Y., Shen, W., and Sharma, A. (2024). UAV T-YOLO-rice: an enhanced tiny yolo networks for rice leaves diseases detection in paddy agronomy. *IEEE Trans. Netw. Sci. Eng.* 11, 1–16. doi: 10.1109/TNSE.2024.3350640
- Wang, W., Huang, Z., Fu, Z., Jia, L., Li, Q., and Song, J. (2024). Impact of digital technology adoption on technological innovation in grain production. *J. Innov. Knowl.* 9:100520. doi: 10.1016/j.jik.2024.100520
- Yang, G., Li, Y., Shen, Y., Changzai, Z., Hongshun, X., Zhenging, Z., et al. (2024). Enhancing direct-seeded rice yield prediction using UAV-derived features acquired during the reproductive phase. *Precision Agric.* 25, 1014–1037. doi: 10.1007/s11119-023-10103-y
- Yang, L., Yu, S., and Liu, B. (2025). The impact of digital literacy on farmland scale operations: exploring the mediating and moderation roles of land transfer and land dependence. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 9:1546024. doi: 10.3389/fsufs.2025.1546024
- Zhou, J., Li, F., Wang, X., Yin, H., Zhang, W., Du, J., and Pu, H. (2024). Hyperspectral and fluorescence imaging approaches for nondestructive detection of rice chlorophyll. *Plants* 13:1270. doi: 10.3390/plants13091270